

DIGITAL TOOLS TO DEVELOP BASIC ENGLISH LANGUAGE PROFICIENCY

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Technological evolution has opened modern skylines for learning and instructing English as a second language. New approaches and tools in Linguistics lead to the effectiveness of the studying process. Learners clearly highlight that speaking is their key issue in real-life interaction caused by different components commencing with prerequisites of the need for inspiration or psychological features. In the early 1980s, computer materials for teaching languages appeared, which are often called CALL (Computer Assisted Language Learning). Programs of this kind, as a rule, required students to respond to visual queries on a computer screen and perform tasks such as filling in missing words in the text, matching halves of sentences, and performing actions with multiple choices. Probably one of the most famous early computer CALL materials is text recovery when the entire text is disabled and the student recreates it by typing words. For all of these activities, the computer then offers the student feedback, ranging from simply indicating whether the answer is correct or incorrect to providing more complex feedback, such as showing why the student is wrong and suggesting corrective actions. The CALL approach is an approach that is still found on many published CDs for language learning [1, p.85].

In Linguodidactics, the term Computer Assisted Language Instruction (CALL) and later Computer-Assisted Language Learning (CALL) ("computer learning of foreign languages", "computer linguodidactics") appeared in connection with the beginning of the active introduction of a computer into the process of teaching foreign languages. However, this concept does not fully include the entire arsenal of modern technologies. With the advent of interactive websites and mobile applications in the field of education, terms such as Electronic Learning (e-learning), Mobile Learning

(m-learning) began to be used. Therefore, now the term Technology-Assisted Foreign Language Learning (TAFL) is considered the most acceptable, most accurately reflects the use of a wide range of ICT in the practice of foreign language education.

Hence, these days emerges an issue of quick and proficient speaking aptitudes that must be taken appropriately. This paper focuses on the investigation of advanced language learning devices and their commonsense utilization both for classroom-based and home practices on the English language for the ESL learners of B1 and B2 levels. The chief results of the current investigation illustrate how common speaking activities can be utilized more successfully by digital tools to advance talking in the target language. Namely, audiobooks with *book creator tool*, pronunciation developer with *Spelling Bee game* that provide maximum chances for learners of the English language study by revising and correcting their own mistakes several times and getting used to real-life communication patterns. The challenge lies in having coherent articulation and precision of the dialect that can be picked up and upgraded through portable applications. Extra benefits incorporate pros of them is developing reproductive skills as Listening and Reading. The use of new information technologies in teaching English helps to improve and optimize the learning process and make the lesson more interesting. We complement and combine traditional teaching methods with new methods, use information technology, apply an individual approach to each student and develop their linguistic abilities, as well as objectively assess the quality of each learner's knowledge.

To conduct the investigation it was vital to browse the Google and Google play store and select the relevant up-to-date free application and compelling speaking practices online, utilize them at the lessons to check their effectiveness and in this way bunch them in understanding with their method of reasoning, down to earth and user-friendly points. The criteria connected to the app included:

- modern and fun ESL activities such as gap filling, dragging the letters/words, matching, etc. that centered on the development of speaking;
- speaking cards or tasks must be upgraded in a certain time;
- learners answers can be recorded and assessed;
- applications are available for both computers and mobile phones.

Most computer programs currently have mobile versions, which makes it possible to use the service from mobile devices. This approach in teaching

foreign languages is called Mobile Assisted Language Learning (MALL) ("Learning foreign languages using mobile technologies"), it allows you to individualize learning by creating personally significant situations for each student and self-regulation of the learning process due to the possibility of choosing the intensity of language learning, to provide direct feedback while diagnosing and correcting errors [2].

Innovative pedagogical tools can develop the playfulness of learners to study and grab their attention easily. Technology gives learners a chance to engage in self-directed actions, opportunities for self-paced interactions, and a safe atmosphere in which errors get corrected and specific feedback is essential to every learner. Namely, **Quizlet**, **TalkEnglish**, **Kahoot**, **Online spelling Bee** were experienced in my lessons and they are considered as most fruitful in teaching speaking. I chose 2 groups of 32 ESL learners who are University freshmen and second-year students, According to my survey, most of them found Kahoot as very interesting and easy to remember, Quizlet as useful and easy to use. Data in the chart is given in numbers.

Quizlet (<https://quizlet.com/>) is a mobile and web-based study application that push learners of English to study vocabulary through learning cards and games. As a memorization tool, Quizlet allows registered users to create vocabulary sets and their definitions specialized for teacher-learner own needs. These sets of words can then be practiced with a number of study types: flashcards, gravity, match, speller, write, long-term learning, test, live. This application is useful when used to recall new vocabulary as homework to be later used at the lesson as it contains pronunciation and thus learners do not struggle in spelling them.

TalkEnglish (<https://www.talkenglish.com/>) is an application with interesting lessons to increase English speaking skills. The quizzes follow after the specific topic and help in figuring out what you learned. Listening exercises and recorded progress show the comprehension level and progress. We should specify that communication skills must be practiced in pairs or in groups. However, there is one important to these applications – they are structured with sets of quizzes to identify and correct mistakes and learn the necessary new words.

The technologies of educational and role-playing games allow for a differentiated approach to students, involving each student in the work, taking into account his interests, aptitude, level of training in the language. Exercises of a playful nature enrich students with new impressions, activate vocabulary, perform a developmental function, relieve fatigue. With their help, you can improve grammatical, lexical skills or form speech skills, develop observation, attention and creativity.

Kahoot (<https://www.kahoot.com/>) An internet, game-based learning application, Kahoot! That engages all the learners, lets you and make and share your answers virtually rapidly and effectively. Instructors can utilize it as warmup movement, to survey concepts they have designed, or as a shape of appraisal. Moreover, it is completely free to utilize! Making your own learning game is the way that learners must think quickly, choose and say it to record up to your choice. Creating the content is easy:

- ❖ The quizzes are designed according to your choice whether it might be true or false, multiple-choice, insert an answer, etc., then you will add the question, appropriate image to it.
- ❖ When your game is ready, you will share the PIN with your students
- ❖ Students log in with unique PIN and play the game on their computer or mobile device

Online spelling Bee game (<https://www.online spellingBee.com/>) Online spelling Bee is a platform with interesting cards to increase vocabulary and obtain spelling with listening. The pictures are given, learners must choose the image and they have to spell. The learners can use their own images and audio clips The quizzes follow after the specific topic and help in figuring out what you learned. Listening exercises and recorded progress show the comprehension level and progress. We should specify that communication skills must be practiced in pairs or in groups. However, there is one important to these applications –they are structured with sets of quizzes to identify and correct mistakes and learn the necessary

new words. However, it is impossible to insert numbers or special characters, they will be automatically removed. This game can improve learners' audio and pronunciation skills.

Modern pedagogical technologies are not only the use of technical means of teaching or computers, it is the identification of principles and the development of methods for optimizing the educational process that increase educational efficiency. As for the practical application of technologies, it is not necessary to use one technology at all. It is best to integrate several educational technologies, combining their best sides. Being engaged in the integration of modern educational technologies in the process of teaching a foreign language for the formation of a student's communicative competence, for a number of years carefully studying, testing and adapting innovative ideas of modern Russian and foreign teachers, one can come to the conclusion that it is this pedagogical system that contributes to the disclosure of a student's subjective experience, the formation of personally significant ways of educational work for him, the upbringing of moral ideals, the development of critical thinking, adequate assessment and self-improvement of each student and the opportunity to realize himself as a person.

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